

Academic Self-Efficacy And Academic Achievement Among Special Education Department Students At The Faculty Of Basic Education And The Relationship Between Them In Light Of Some Variables

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 28, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Academic Self, Efficacy, Academic Specialization, Academic Rate</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4640545</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed at revealing the level of academic self-efficacy and its relationship to academic achievement among students of special education in the College of Basic Education in the light of some variables. To achieve the goals of the study, the academic self-efficacy measure was used. The researcher used the comparative descriptive approach for several reasons and its relevance to the study's goals. The study sample consisted of (215) students in the Department of Special Education, College of Basic Education. The results of the study showed, in general, that the total score for the level of academic self-efficacy among students was an average degree. It also indicated a statistically significant positive correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement of the study sample. Also, there were apparent differences between arithmetic means in academic self-efficacy in all variables where they were statistically significant only according to the academic average. It was attributed to those with a perfect and excellent academic average.</i></p>

Introduction

The special education teacher is the goal of every educational system that believes in educating students with disabilities to face the challenges of the current era. Still, the shortage of qualified special education teachers has led to general education teachers' employment to teach students with disabilities in Kuwait's schools, despite their lack of scientific qualification to work with these students of special needs.

This situation for educating students with disabilities has prompted more desire to prepare special education teachers in the College of Basic Education by establishing a special education department that prepares and graduates special education teachers with competence in several disciplines. Preparing special education teachers requires providing them with relevant programs, high efficiency, and keeping pace with this field's existing development. As the special education teacher teaches students with disabilities, which requires more intensive education, knowledge, and special skills to teach them better, link new learning methods with previous knowledge, and acquire new ideas and skills (Lyon, Shogren & Kurth, 2015). Therefore, the concept of academic self-efficacy was viewed as an educational and skill indicator for special education teachers who should be more able to deal with the challenges of teaching students with disabilities.

Bandura (1986) elucidated that the study of academic self-efficacy has received increasing attention in recent years and has sought to identify the individual's ability to achieve a certain level of accomplishment, his ability to control the situations, what goals he seeks to achieve, the amount of effort he exerts, and the extent of his perseverance in addressing the problems he faces.

Academic self-efficacy is a characteristic of the personality, and it represents the individual's beliefs about his capabilities and abilities by succeeding in performing certain tasks (Betz, 2004). Students with high academic self-efficacy make great effort and show perseverance and high flexibility in facing different educational situations, contributing a great deal to cognitive growth that leads to academic success (Bandura, 2000).

Moreover, Academic self-efficacy is a strong indicator of the teacher's ability to cope with the challenges he faced in his early years of teaching and an indicator of his classroom effectiveness and motivation. Furthermore, it reflects his confidence in meeting students' different needs, encouraging them to learn and increase their academic achievement (Lombardo, 2017).

Studies dealing with teachers' effectiveness in special education indicated that teachers with higher levels of academic self-efficacy make fewer referrals for students to receive special education services and feel more responsible for them (Freitag, 2001).

Academic self-efficacy is important when preparing special education teachers. They need to develop specialized skills to teach students with disabilities, such as the knowledge of special education laws and

legislation, cooperation with others, implementation and application of the individual education program, support for students and parents' rights, and provision of services moves beyond school education (Taylor, 2012).

A special education teacher with high academic self-efficacy is more capable of bearing the responsibility of educating students with disabilities, fewer students' referrals to special education programs, and more able to address educational and behavioral problems and their role in regular schools (Paneque & Barbetta, 2006).

Undergraduate students experience a critical developmental stage in their lives as individuals, and it is linked on the one hand to the changes in their beliefs about themselves, and on the other hand, the expectations from new educational and social contexts. A sense of identity emerges from the student's ability to overcome social and academic requirements (Luyckx, et al., 2007). Accordingly, the individual's self-efficacy will influence learning and academic achievement (Valentine, Dubois & Cooper, 2004).

Good academic achievement accomplishes the required compatibility between the productivity of the educational system and its outputs and the actual need for various fields of work of qualified and trained human energies. Besides, it guarantees the principle of equal educational opportunities, which is one of the most important principles on which the democracy of education is based (Salem, 2005).

Academic achievement is considered an important indicator that affects the individual's life and develops his mental abilities, which works in harmony between the individual's behavior and emotions. Also, it depends primarily on the student's abilities, experience, skill, training, and the surrounding circumstances towards achieving the highest levels of achievement and realizations (Abujado and Al-Sayyad, 2017).

Academic self-efficacy is associated with high achievement levels and many adaptive academic outcomes such as high levels of perseverance and increasing persistence in performing difficult, complex tasks and using strategies for the cognitive organization (Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002).

Despite the importance of academic self-efficacy in achieving academic achievement and success, the researcher did not find studies dealing with this relationship on special education students at the undergraduate level. Besides, some studies tried to examine the level of academic self-efficacy only without linking it to academic achievement to know the extent of the relationship between them and their direction.

Ross and Hammer (2002) conducted a study that dealt with the relationship between adjustment, academic achievement, parenting styles, and identity styles. The sample was (106) students from the University of Wisconsin in the United States. The study results indicated an impact and relationship of identity styles and parenting styles on academic achievement and adaptation among university students, as the results of the study showed, the existence of a statistically significant predictive ability of the standard identity method of adaptation.

Also, Jakubowski & Dembo (2004) sought to determine the relationship between academic self-regulation and self-efficacy, two systems of self-beliefs, and identity styles where the sample was (210) students from a private university. The study results revealed a strong correlation between informational style, self-efficacy, and academic self-regulation, as the correlation coefficient between informational style and self-efficacy reached (0.67) and the predictive ability of the standard and chaotic method did not appear.

In their study, Berzonsky & Kulk (2004) dealt with the relationship between identity style, psychosocial normalization, and academic achievement on a sample of (460) male and female students. The study results indicated that students with the informational identity style had high academic performance and achieved high academic self-efficacy levels, with clear educational goals and social skills compared to students with distracted or avoidant identity style.

Hegazy, et al. (2008) conducted a study to determine the mean of self-efficacy effect on the relationship between identity styles and academic achievement on a sample of (400) male and female students, using path analysis. The study results showed a positive effect on achievement for the informational, academic method and a negative effect on the avoidance method. The study also indicated a positive effect of the standard method and information on academic achievement through the mediating relationship of self-efficacy.

Devonport & Lane (2003) carried out a study that dealt with the relationship between academic self-efficacy and facing difficulties and studying at the university. The sample consisted of 87 male and 44 female students from the College of Physical Education in the United Kingdom. The study results indicated that those with high academic self-efficacy have a great ability to face challenges. They scored the highest in university continuation and have a positive correlation with academic success.

Among the studies that dealt with academic self-efficacy and its relationship to variables: gender, academic level, and academic specialization are the Telez study (1997), where it examined perceived self-efficacy among a sample of first and fourth-year undergraduate students and reached no statistically significant differences between both university levels.

Lemons (2005) carried out a study to identify the level of academic self-efficacy perceived for students' creativity. He presented a questionnaire consisting of open-ended questions, asking students what they think

about their creativity, and found that most of the sample members do not have a high awareness of their academic self-efficacy for creativity.

Rapoo (2001) conducted a study to examine the relationship between the perception of educational practices, gender, academic self-efficacy, and academic achievement among secondary school students in South Africa, and the study sample consisted of (113) students. The results showed that the relationship between perceived self-efficacy and gender was not statistically significant.

Finn & Frone (2004) studied the relationship between academic performance, academic self-efficacy, cheating, and the impact of gender, age, and academic level. The research sample consisted of (315) male and female students selected from three colleges. The two researchers applied a measure of academic performance and academic self-efficacy. After collecting data and conducting appropriate statistical analyzes, a statistically significant relationship was found between age, gender, academic average, self-efficacy, and academic performance.

After reviewing the previous studies that the researcher could obtain, several studies addressed the variable of academic self-efficacy and its relationship to some other variables such as academic performance, gender, academic average, ability to adapt, parenting styles, identity methods, academic self-organization, and facing difficulties and continuation at the university. Most studies used the descriptive approach to achieve their objectives, and many of them were conducted on random samples mainly taken from university students as in this study. Also, several studies used correlation factors and statistical laws related to conducting and building measurement tools, including those related to the answer to the study's questions. The four-way MANOVA analysis of variance was used to examine the significance of the differences between the arithmetic means. The Pearson correlation coefficient was extracted to examine the relationship between academic self-efficacy and the level of academic achievement. According to the academic average, the Scheffé test was used to examine the significance of the differences between the arithmetic averages of academic self-efficacy levels.

Previous studies used several measuring tools that differ according to various goals. Researchers built a number of them, and other researchers adopted tools designed by others after researchers' translation to suit the nature of the study goals and their sample. In this study, the researcher took a foreign scale, translated it into Arabic, and applied it to the common Arab culture environments with the study sample, and validity and constancy specific to this study were extracted.

Most of the earlier studies were conducted on university environments that were different from the College of Basic Education environments, so generalizing their results in the current study is not possible, which indicates the need to conduct this study. Moreover, the results of earlier studies, despite their agreement on the relationship between academic self-competence and academic achievement, however, the results on the dependent variables such as gender, academic level, and academic specialization were inconsistent, which justifies the need for this study.

The Problem of the Study:

The researcher's study problem crystallized after studying the theoretical literature and previous studies that dealt with the study variables and noticed a big difference between academic achievement and academic self-competence during the teaching process. The researcher sought to verify this observation scientifically. Therefore, this study came to find out the level of academic self-competence and reveal the relationship between it. The academic achievement of students of the Special Education Department at the College of Basic Education in Kuwait in light of some variables (gender - specialization - school year - academic average), and more precisely, the current study tried to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of academic self-efficacy among the Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education?
2. Is there a relationship between students' grades on the scale of academic self-efficacy and their academic achievement level among the Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education?
3. Are there differences between the study sample members on the scale of academic self-efficacy according to (gender - academic specialization - school year - academic average)?

Significance of the study:

This study will provide a theoretical building in educational situations, thus helping the educators in charge of the teaching process in the special education departments to build their educational plans.

- Knowing the level of academic self-efficacy among students of the Special Education Department of the College of Basic Education improves and develops teaching methods, educational and professional guidance, and counseling.
- The evaluation of special education department students through the academic self-efficacy scale is necessary to make sure that teacher preparation programs effectively raise these students' academic self-competence.
- The special education teacher bears a great responsibility in helping students with disabilities to enable them to succeed. Raising their academic self-efficacy is of the utmost importance.

Objectives of the study:

The current study mainly aimed to reveal the level of academic self-efficacy and its relationship to academic achievement among Special Education students at the College of Basic Education in light of some variables, namely gender, academic specialization, academic year, and academic average.

Limitations of the study:

Objective boundaries: The subject of the study was determined in the detection of academic self-efficacy level and its relationship to academic achievement among students of special education at the College of Basic Education.

Individual Limitations: This study was limited to a sample of students in the Special Education Department.

Time limitations: This study was conducted during the second semester of the 2019/2020 academic year.

Spatial limitations: College of Basic Education in Kuwait.

The terminology of study:

Academic self-efficacy: It refers to the individual's perceived beliefs about the extent of his ability to carry out certain academic tasks, measured by the overall score obtained by the respondent on the scale of academic self-efficacy, which was used for the current study.

Academic specialization: refers to the field to which students belong in the Special Education Department of the College of Basic Education.

Academic average: It refers to the student's grades on the four-point scale after passing the academic courses during the period he spent in the Special Education Department of the College of Basic Education.

Study Methodology and Procedures:

Study Approach:

In this study, the descriptive and comparative approach of causes and correlation was used for its suitability for the study's objectives, which is the appropriate approach to the research's nature. This study requires collecting data for several variables, comparing them, and finding the comparison level as an accurate description, and expressing them qualitatively or quantitatively.

Study population:

The study population consists of all Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education who are registered for the second semester of the 2019/2020 academic year. There are (2330) students, according to the records of the Admission and Registration Office.

The Sample of the study:

A stratified random sample of (215) male and female students was selected with a percentage of 5% of the Special Education Department of the College of Basic Education students. The table also shows the study sample's distribution according to gender, academic specialization, academic year, and academic average.

Table (1) Distribution of the study sample

Academic Average			Academic Year				Academic Specialization			Gender	
Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fourth	Third	Second	First	Excelling mind	Learning Difficulty	Mental Disability	Female	Male
73	114	28	73	94	46	2	89	81	45	155	60
215			215				215			215	

The instrument of the Study

For this study, the researcher used the academic self-efficacy scale built by Omen & Fromen (1988), referred to in AlBadarin and Ghaith (2013). The scale consists of (33) items translated into Arabic and modified to suit the Arab environment. The stability of the internal consistency in the original scale is (90.0). The consistency in the re-test method is (85.0), where the total score on the scale represents the level of the student's ability to academic self-efficacy. The researcher developed the scale to fit the Kuwaiti environment by making sure of its validity and stability as follows:

First: Validate the content:

The validity of the content of the first study instrument (academic self-competence) was verified by distributing it to a group of experienced and competent arbitrators, taking their opinions and suggestions, and making the necessary adjustments that (80%) of the arbitrators agreed upon. The study tool in its final form consisted of (32) items.

Second: Building Validity Indicators:

The correlation coefficients of the items with the total score of the Self-Efficiency Scale were extracted, and Table (2) shows that.

Table (2) the values of the items correlation coefficients with the total degree

Number of Items	Correlation Total Degree Coefficient	Number of Items	Correlation Total Degree Coefficient	Number of Items	Total Degree Coefficient
1	0.67**	12	0.54**	23	0.62**
2	0.56**	13	0.59**	24	0.54**
3	0.49**	14	0.71**	25	0.86**
4	0.73**	15	0.54**	26	0.57**
5	0.54**	16	0.65**	27	0.49**
6	0.43**	17	0.67**	28	0.48**
7	0.58**	18	0.52**	29	0.45**
8	0.57**	19	0.76**	30	0.56**
9	0.59**	20	0.80**	31	0.54**
10	0.47**	21	0.65**	32	0.49**
11	0.54**	22	0.85**		

It is noted from the results of Table (2) that the values of the correlation coefficients were all statistically significant and exceeded (0.30), which indicated that the scale had appropriate construct validity.

Stability of the study tool:

The study's consistency was verified by applying it to an exploratory sample that consisted of (30) students who are not included in the study population, and the application was repeated after two weeks. Pearson correlation coefficient was found between the two times of the application where the value was (0.88). The internal consistency was calculated using Cronbach's alpha equation, and its value was (0.85).

Study tool correction:

The arithmetic averages were described according to the following equation:
(The highest value in the ranking - the lowest value)

Table (3)
The description of the arithmetic averages

Number of classes	1.33
Low	2.33 - 1
Moderate	3.67 - 2.34

High	5 - 3.68
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Results:

The first question of the study states: What is the level of academic self-efficacy among the Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education?

The arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted to answer this question, and Table (4) shows that.

Table (4) the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the level of academic Self-efficacy among students of the Special Education Department arranged in descending order.

Sequence	Item	Arithmetic Mean	standard deviation	Rank	level
16	Participation in extracurricular activities, seminars, exhibitions, associations	4.67	0.65	16	high
17	Make your teachers respect and appreciate you	4.51	0.74	17	high
19	A commitment to attend boring lectures regularly	4.39	0.95	19	high
12	Ask your teacher to re-explain a concept that you did not understand	4.23	0.84	12	high
30	Use and benefit from the college library	4.20	0.86	30	high
5	To answer a small number of questions asked by the teachers	4.19	0.96	5	high
18	The commitment to attend school lectures regularly	4.17	1.05	18	high
21	Understand most of the concepts and ideas that are mentioned in the examination paper	4.09	0.85	21	high
13	Get good grades in most of the subjects	4.07	0.96	13	high
20	Make your professors think that you are giving your full attention to the lecture	4.07	0.89	20	high
4	To answer a large number of questions posed by the teachers	3.93	1.22	4	high
8	Writing a high-quality research or semester report	3.93	1.08	8	high
26	Talk to your teachers privately to get to know them	3.76	1.05	26	high
1	Take structured and coherent notes during a lecture.	3.73	1.10	1	high
6	Passing the tests with objective questions	3.66	1.14	6	moderate
31	Get high marks	3.64	1.20	31	moderate
2	Take structured and coherent notes during the lecture	3.63	1.26	2	moderate
32	Distributing and organizing study times on academic subjects	3.59	1.03	32	moderate
10	Teaching some of your classmates some academic subjects and lessons	3.53	1.24	10	moderate
28	Challenge, oppose the opinions and ideas of your teachers in classroom lectures	3.53	1.10	28	moderate
24	Use the computer efficiently	3.45	1.06	24	moderate
22	Understand most of the concepts and ideas presented in the lectures	3.39	1.28	22	moderate
11	Explain and interpretation of a scientific concept to a colleague in a subject	3.36	1.28	11	moderate
7	Pass the essay-related exams	3.34	1.16	7	moderate
3	Participate in class discussions	3.33	1.21	3	moderate
9	Listening throughout the study lecture on a difficult and complex topic	3.33	1.26	9	moderate
14	Study the course material enough to understand its content fully	3.31	1.31	14	moderate
33	Understand difficult texts in textbooks and courses	3.14	1.20	33	moderate
23	Perform simple math operations	3.05	1.29	23	moderate
27	Linking the course content to each other	2.63	1.32	27	moderate
29	Employ the course content you have learned in an applied scientific situation	2.58	1.43	29	moderate
25	Master the most challenging scientific content	2.47	1.40	25	moderate

15	Explain a scientific issue or study in front of your classmates	2.36	1.36	15	moderate
	Total	3.61	0.85	moderate	

It is noticed from Table (4) that the arithmetic average of the college grade for the level of academic self-efficacy among students of the Special Education Department of the College of Basic Education reached (3.61) with a standard deviation (0.85). Item (16) came in the first rank, which stated "Participation in extracurricular activities (seminars, exhibitions associations)" with arithmetic mean (4.67) and a standard deviation (0.65) with a high degree. In the last rank came item (15), which stated, "Explain a scientific issue or study in front of your classmates", with an arithmetic mean (2.36) and a standard deviation (1.36) with a moderate degree.

The results of the second question, which states:

Is there a relationship between students' grades on the scale of academic self-efficacy and their academic achievement level among the Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education?

To answer this question, Pearson's correlation coefficient was extracted between the measure of academic self-efficacy and their level of academic achievement. The correlation coefficient value was (0.40), which is a statistically significant function at ($\alpha = 0.05$), as it indicates a positive correlation.

The results of the third study question, which states:

Are there differences between the study sample members on academic self-efficacy scale according to (gender - academic specialization - academic year - academic average)?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the Academic Self-Efficiency Scale were extracted according to (gender - academic specialization - academic year - academic average), as seen in Table (5).

(Table 5)

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the academic self-efficacy scale according to (gender - academic specialization - academic year - academic average)

Gender	Number	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations
Male	60	3.67	0.51
Female	155	3.58	0.56
Total	215	3.61	0.54
Academic Specialization	Number	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations
Mental disability	45	3.66	0.48
Learning difficulties	81	3.62	0.58
Mental superiority	89	3.58	0.54
Total	215	3.61	0.54
Academic Year	Number	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations
First-year	2	4.30	0.45
Second-year	46	3.64	0.52
Third-year	94	3.60	0.51
Fourth-year	73	3.60	0.60
Total marks	215	3.60	0.54
Academic Average	Number	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations

Good	28	3.21	0.50
Very good	114	3.56	0.50
Excellent	73	3.85	0.52
Total	215	3.61	0.54

It is noted from Table (5) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the level of academic self-efficacy according to (gender - academic specialization - school year - academic average). To find out whether these differences are statistically significant, the four-way MANOVA variable analysis was extracted as seen in Table (6).

Table (6)

The results of the analysis of variance test to examine the significance of the differences between the arithmetic averages of the level of academic self-efficacy according to (gender, academic specialization, academic year, and academic average)

source of Variance	Sum of squares	degree of freedom	means of squares	F	level of significance
Gender	.672	1	.672	2.683	0.103
Specialization	.734	3	.245	.977	0.404
Year	1.568	3	.523	2.088	0.103
The error	9.505	2	4.753	18.987	0.000*
Total	51.314	205	.250		
Corrected Total	2869.686	215			

Statistical function at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level

It is noted from Table (6) results that there were no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic averages of the level of academic self-efficacy according to gender, academic specializations, and academic year. As the significance values for "f" were greater than (0.05) for each case, while the results showed the existence of statistically significant differences according to the academic average, as the value of "f" was (18.987) as shown in Table (7).

Table (7)

Scheffé test results to examine the significance of differences between arithmetic means arithmetic averages for academic self-efficacy level according to the academic average.

Academic Average Levels	Arithmetic Mean	Good	Very Good	Excellent
Good	3.21	-	0.35-*	0.64-*
Very Good	3.56	-	-	0.29-*
Excellent	3.85	-	-	-

It is noted from the results of Table (7) that the differences between the arithmetic averages of the level of academic self-efficacy according to the academic average are attributable to those with an academic average of (very good) and (excellent).

Discussion of the results:

The results indicated that the level of academic self-efficacy among the Special Education Department students was average, with an arithmetic average of (3.61), which could be attributed to the students being encountered in a new study environment different from the school. This may expose them to failure experiences that may cause them to decline in their beliefs about their abilities. The study results agreed with Lemons' (2005) findings, where it was found that the majority of the sample individuals do not have a high awareness of their academic self-efficacy on creativity. However, this result contradicted Brzonsky and Kulk's (2004) study, where the results indicated students had achieved high levels of academic self-efficacy.

To answer the second question, is there a relationship between students' grades on the scale of academic self-efficacy and their academic achievement level among the Special Education Department students in the College of Basic Education? Pearson's correlation coefficient was extracted between the measure of academic self-efficacy and their level of academic achievement. The correlation coefficient value was (0.04), which is a statistically significant function of ($\alpha = 0.05$), which indicates a positive correlation relationship. This result was consistent with the findings of Jakubowski & Dembo (2004) of the existence of a strong correlation between informational style, self-efficacy, and academic self-regulation, also with the findings of Devonport and Lane (2003) on the existence of a positive correlation between academic success and academic self-efficacy as well as Hejazi, et al., (2008) study.

The third question results showed apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the level of academic self-efficacy according to (gender - academic specialization - school year - academic average). After extracting the four-way MANOVA variance analysis, it was found that there are no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the level of academic self-efficacy according to gender, academic specialization, and academic year. This result was consistent with the findings of Telez's study (1997). He studied perceived self-efficacy among a sample of first and fourth-year undergraduate students and reached no statistically significant differences between both university levels. The results were also compatible with the findings of Rapoo (2001) that the relationship between perceived self-efficacy and gender was not statistically significant. On the other hand, the results showed statistically significant differences according to the academic average and the knowledge feedback of these differences. A Scheffé test for dimensional comparisons was extracted. It was found that the differences between the arithmetic averages of the level of Academic self-efficacy according to the academic average is attributed to those with an academic rate of (very good) and (excellent). They are eager to achieve accomplishments and are interested in developing their academic capabilities to achieve their goals and future ambitions. This result was consistent with Finn and Frone's (2004) findings, with a statistically significant relationship between academic average, self-efficacy, and academic performance.

Conclusion:

In general, the study results showed that the overall score for the level of academic self-efficacy among students of the Special Education Department in the College of Basic Education came with a moderate degree. The results also showed a positive, statistically significant correlation relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement of the study sample. The study found clear differences between the arithmetic means in the level of academic self-efficacy in all the variables and was statistically significant according to the academic average only and attributed to those with an academic average of (very good) and (excellent). This study results were consistent with some studies. They differed from others, which enriches scientific research in academic self-efficacy among students of the Department of Special Education. Therefore, counseling programs should be provided to improve their academic self-efficacy and create environments that encourage them to adapt and develop their academic capabilities and ensure motivating students with low grades and developing their skills, and working on creating courses for raising their level of academic self-efficacy. The researcher can also conduct more studies dealing with academic self-efficacy with other variables that serve them to achieve accomplishment.

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